

How Do Stress-Related Disorders Affect Frontal lobe Functions In Adolescents And Young Adults?

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ABSTRACT

The brain develops rapidly during adolescence and early adulthood, particularly in the frontal lobe, which is crucial for brain skills, emotional control, and decision-making. The brain's frontal lobe controls reasoning, planning, movement, speech, personality, and many other cognitive, motor, and emotional processes. It plays a significant role in stress management and is linked explicitly in several ways to disorders associated with stress. Anxiety and depression, two stress-related diseases that are common during these periods of life, can have a significant impact on brain function. The purpose of this study is to look at how stress-related diseases, like separation anxiety disorder or panic disorder, impact young adults' and adolescents' frontal lobe function. The present study will observe functional changes in the frontal lobe associated with stress-related disorders. It will examine the correlation between the severity of stress-related symptoms and frontal lobe impairment. This research attempts to improve understanding of how stress affects brain function throughout critical developmental periods by identifying particular changes in the frontal lobe. This study also aims to contribute to developing specific measures meant to lessen these adverse effects.

Keywords: *Frontal lobe, stress-related disorders, cognitive functions, adolescents, and neurotransmitters*

1. INTRODUCTION

Stress-related disorders, such as anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), are increasingly prevalent among adolescents and young adults. Studies suggest that approximately 1 in 5 U.S. adults and 1 in 6 U.S. youth ages 6-17 experience a mental health disorder each year (NAMI, 2024). This high frequency is concerning, given that the brain's frontal lobe is still developing during adolescence. While arguably the most important for complex day-to-day tasks, the frontal lobe is prone to brain injuries because this part of the brain

is at the very front of the head (Cleveland Clinic, 2022). This makes it also vulnerable to being affected by stress-related disorders. Extensive scientific research on the frontal cortex has revealed that dysfunction in this region is related to many mental health conditions. Understanding mental illness in youth is essential for understanding cognitive and emotional outcomes across the lifespan; for example, the literature suggests that adolescent depression may increase the risk for poor mental health outcomes in adulthood (Johnson et al., 2018).

This paper aims to examine the impact of stress-related disorders on the structure and function of the frontal lobe in adolescents. A narrative review explores the anatomy and functions of the frontal lobe and outlines the symptomatology of stress-related disorders. A discussion outlines the relationship between frontal lobes and stress-related disorders in adolescents and details various therapeutic approaches, including pharmacological treatments and cognitive therapies.

1.2 ANATOMY AND FUNCTION OF FRONTAL LOBE

The frontal lobe is one of the four major lobes of the brain, located at the front of the cerebral cortex, just behind the forehead. Experts estimate that the frontal lobe comprises 25% to 40% of the brain's cerebral cortex, which consists of neurons, cells responsible for transmitting electrical and chemical signals in the brain, and glial cells, the nervous system's support cells (Cleveland Clinic, 2022). This area of the brain is primarily responsible for what are collectively referred to as executive functions. These include the ability to pay attention, reason, make decisions, solve problems, regulate emotions, and be aware of how oneself and others are operating (Scott & Schoenberg, 2010).

The frontal lobe controls voluntary muscle movements through the primary motor cortex (Cleveland Clinic, 2022). In humans, developing a complex network of short and long-range connections ensures immediate access to sensory data. Also, areas within the frontal lobes are specialized for planning and executing physical movements (Catani, 2024). For example, Broca's area contributes to cognitive control and motor speech production (Novick et al., 2010). The orbitofrontal cortex processes rewards and punishments. Medial activity in this region is focused on monitoring rewards, while lateral activity assesses punishers (Kringelbach & Rolls, 2004). Damage to this area results in changes that interfere with the ability to interact with other people

(Denslow, 2022). For example, this could lead to poor decision-making skills, impulsive behavior, or decreased emotional responses.

The dorsolateral prefrontal cortex is vital in remembering and altering spatial information related to predictable action sequences. Damage can result in repetitive, compulsive behavior and personality changes (Fremont et al., 2022). Also, the ventral-medial cortex specializes in decision-making, social cognition, and social judgment (Muzur and Hobson, in Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 2002). This cortex being damaged is shown to impair higher-order behavioral guidance, social conduct, and emotional regulation (Hernandez et al., 2009). The development of the frontal lobe goes through significant changes during childhood, which affect executive functions. For instance, synaptic pruning is a natural process that removes unnecessary synapses from the brain, allowing for more efficient neural transmissions and healthy brain development (Rowden, 2023). The brain's pruning process can affect executive functions by eliminating too many synapses or neural connections or slowing down the pruning process (Edge Foundations, 2023). Frontal lobe functioning develops from early childhood to adolescence and into early adulthood but has a decreased rate after maturation (Romine & Reynolds, 2005).

In conclusion, the frontal lobe is an integral part of the brain that controls motor control, social cognition, and executive functions, which are necessary for daily activities. Damage to this region can significantly impact behavior, personality, and interactions with others because of its function in movement, emotional regulation, and decision-making. Addressing problems associated with cognitive and emotional health requires an awareness of the frontal lobe's functions because it continues to grow until early adulthood. Understanding the frontal lobe can help improve brain function and assist with successful treatments if damage is caused.

1.3 STRESS-RELATED DISORDERS

Stress-related disorders are mental health conditions that arise from exposure to traumatic or stressful experiences. These disorders impact an individual's social and professional functioning and may cause psychological distress (Martins-Monteverde et al., 2017). Stress symptoms may negatively impact an individual's health, even if they are unaware of the stressors in their life. Their body, feelings, and behavior can all be affected by stress symptoms. Awareness of common stress symptoms can help people manage and cope with the effects of stress (Mayo Clinic Staff, 2023). Ignored stress can cause a variety of health issues, including high blood pressure, heart

disease, stroke, obesity, and diabetes (Mayo Clinic Staff, 2023). The prevalence of stress-related disorders has been increasing across the country. For example, the lifetime prevalence of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) was reported to be 7.8% among study participants, who were representative of the general US population aged 15–54 years, in survey research conducted in the US using the DSM criteria for diagnosis (Kessler et al., 1995). One of the most common stress-related disorders, PTSD, arises after going through a traumatic incident. Symptoms include intrusive memories, avoidance, negative changes in thinking and mood, and changes in physical and emotional reactions (Mayo Clinic, 2024).

Anxiety, depression, and Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) are all linked to stress exposure and have a major influence on teenagers' social lives and mental health. OCD, the existence of obsessions or compulsions, is also connected to stress exposure, with a 1.6% lifetime prevalence (Veale & Roberts, 2014). Adolescents with this disease may avoid interacting with their peers or lose their ability to live independently, which lowers their quality of life (Veale & Roberts, 2014). Another common disorder is depression, which is caused by an imbalance of neurotransmitters, genetics, medical conditions, or medications (Cleveland Clinic, 2023). Its significance in the field is shown by research that links depression with self-esteem, particularly as rates of depression increase worldwide (Wilson & Krane, 1980). Anxiety, a common stress-related disorder, especially among younger generations, is closely associated. Although it is expected to experience anxiety at times, when it reaches clinical levels, it can have a significant negative influence on relationships, efficiency at work, and academic achievement. In adolescents, an estimated 31.9% experience any given anxiety disorder like social anxiety, generalized anxiety, or phobias. Adolescent females have a greater prevalence of anxiety disorders compared to men, but the prevalence of any anxiety disorder was similar across age groups (National Institution of Mental Health, 2003).

To summarize, stress-related disorders have negative influences on both mental and physical health, highlighting the pressing need for efficient treatment. In addition to being widespread, disorders including PTSD, OCD, depression, and anxiety have a significant impact on social, academic, and professional functioning. Individuals can better manage stress and avoid its long-term health effects by knowing the symptoms and risk factors linked to these disorders. Creating accessible and supportive networks is essential for enhancing the quality of life for those impacted by stress-related disorders.

2. DISCUSSION

2.1 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FRONTAL LOBES AND STRESS-RELATED DISORDERS

The frontal lobe is implicated in many aspects of stress and stress-related disorders that impact our daily lives. These effects may vary depending on the disorder. The prefrontal cortex also assists in regulating emotional responses initiated by the amygdala (CHAMP, Human Performance Resource Center, 30 May 2017). Neuroimaging studies have shown that individuals with OCD have differences in their brains compared to healthy individuals (Queensland Brain Institute). Specifically, research indicates that individuals with OCD exhibit increased activity in frontal brain regions, such as the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) and orbitofrontal cortex (OFC), which may account for their elevated anxiety levels and intrusive thoughts (Queensland Brain Institute). There is evidence that depression may cause numerous areas of the brain to shrink (Bhandari, 2022). In particular, gray matter volume (GMV) decreases in several regions, including the prefrontal cortex, hippocampus, anterior cingulate cortex, and amygdala. GMV is composed of many brain cells in that tissue. Those with severe symptoms of depression who experience regular or persistent depression appear to have an immense GMV loss, especially in the frontal cortex (Bhandari, 2022). This may result in memory problems, guilt, appetite problems, apathy, or having trouble thinking clearly (Bhandari, 2022).

Changes in the frontal lobe can contribute to stress-related disorders. Frontal lobe abnormalities impact the conditioned fear extinction circuit, the salience circuit, and the mood circuit pertinent to PTSD. In PTSD, functional studies of the frontal cortex reveal abnormal activity in all three based on task demand and emotional intensity (Selemon et al., 2019). When a frontal lobe abnormality causes a stress-related disorder, it could contribute to other dysfunctions within the frontal lobe, such as impaired decision-making, poor impulse control, difficulty with planning and organization, memory loss, and significant personality changes (Cleveland Clinic, 2022).

In summary, the frontal lobe is an essential component in stress-related disorders like OCD, depression, and PTSD. These disorders significantly influence particular frontal lobe areas, including the prefrontal cortex, anterior cingulate cortex, and orbitofrontal cortex. These

disorders cause variations in the structure and activity of the brain that affect cognitive, emotional, and decision-making abilities.

2.1 TREATMENTS

In adolescents and young adults, the damage to the frontal lobe caused by stress-related disorders may lead to difficulties in everyday functioning. The brain can heal itself with new brain cells growing to replace the damaged ones and find new pathways to bypass broken connections (Helliwell, 2019). Understanding how to repair brain damage caused by ongoing stress is critical for recovering cognitive function and improving mental health outcomes.

Understanding the damage caused by ongoing stress is critical for recovering cognitive function and improving mental health outcomes. Anticholinergic medications may be recommended for long-term cognitive impairments caused by disorders like schizophrenia. However, they are often avoided due to adverse side effects (Hadanny & Efrati, 2016). Other medication options are SSRIs/SNRIs and MAOI inhibitors. The effectiveness of these drugs depends on the type of disorder and medication. For example, SSRIs/SNRIs increase serotonin levels in the brain, potentially helping with the symptoms of anxiety and depression (Villines, 2024). MAOIs ease depression by affecting chemical messengers (neurotransmitters) used to communicate between brain cells (Mayo Clinic Staff, 2019). Benzodiazepine and beta-blockers are other medications that can alter emotional and physical stress responses and reduce anxiety. They also impair executive functions, attention, and working memory.

Non-pharmacological treatments, including physical therapy, educational programs, and speech therapy, may be helpful when stress significantly impacts someone's daily activities (Weil et al., 2022). Physical activity benefits brain health by increasing blood flow and the growth of new neurons in areas related to mood and cognition. Educational and speech therapies will improve communication skills and learning strategies and help manage behavior. Exposure to these treatments will help to maintain or regain mobility and strength in the frontal lobe if someone is diagnosed with PTSD. Moreover, regardless of the type of non-pharmacological treatment used, this will help people learn new strategies for daily tasks and activities to improve their well-being (Physiopedia contributors, 2023). Psychotherapy, including cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), dialectical behavior therapy (DBT), Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR), and family systems therapy, may also be helpful. CBT is an effective

therapy that helps people manage stress-related disorders by changing how they think and behave (Mayo Clinic Staff, 2019). It reduces symptoms of various mental health conditions, primarily depression, PTSD, and anxiety disorders (Mayo Clinic Staff, 2019). DBT is a type of psychotherapy that helps people learn to manage their emotions, improve relationships, and tolerate distress (Cleveland, 2022). It can help treat mood and personality disorders (Cleveland, 2022). EMDR is recommended for PTSD, which helps people process traumatic memories and other distressing life experiences (Cleveland, 2022). Family systems therapy is based on the idea that a family is an emotional unit and that what happens to one person affects the entire family (Psychology Today Staff, 2022). Neurofeedback therapy is another safe and efficient treatment for stress-related disorders. One of its best features is that it can provide long-lasting effects without additional sessions (Drake Institute of Neurophysical Medicine, 2024). Other medical treatments include Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS), Electroconvulsive Therapy (ECT), and biofeedback.

Additionally, surgery may be recommended in cases when an injury or brain tumor is causing structural damage. Due to the frontal lobe's numerous tasks, various behavior changes can be associated with structural damage. For example, one may be unable to solve problems, have reduced creativity, impaired judgment, reduced sense of taste or smell, low motivation, low attention span, or risky behavior (Physiopedia, 2023). After surgery, relaxation techniques may be used (Lanini et al., 2022). As well as practicing healthy habits and going to therapy. This will reduce stress, creating a peaceful environment.

In conclusion, addressing long-term cognitive and emotional well-being in adolescents and young adults requires addressing stress-related disorders. Non-pharmacological approaches like CBT, EMDR, and neurofeedback provide efficient treatments. In addition, pharmacological therapies, like SSRIs and anticholinergics, can also aid recovery. When combined with supportive therapy, physical activity, and lifestyle changes, these treatments improve strength and normal daily activities, particularly in those whose frontal lobes have been impacted by long-term stress.

3. CONCLUSION

Despite making up two-thirds of the human brain, the functions of the frontal lobes have long been ill-defined. Before the last 20 years, little information was available regarding the functions

of the frontal lobes outside of their involvement in language and motor function (Chayer & Freedman, 2001). More recent research has revealed the critical roles of the frontal lobes in various tasks (Chayer & Freedman, 2001). Still, the specific functions of neurotransmitters—chemical messengers that carry signals between neurons, muscles, and glands—remain only partially understood. For example, the role of glutamate and gamma-aminobutyric acid balance in the pathophysiology of stress-related disorders like depression is not well understood (Ghosal et al., 2017). One problem that has hindered the complete knowledge of the effects is the need for more techniques to manipulate each interneuron subtype selectively (Ghosal et al., 2017). Increasing the number of techniques would allow researchers to understand the specific roles of the cells in each brain function, which could lead to more effective treatments for stress-related disorders. Moreover, analysis of gender-specific differences in stress-induced effects on GABA interneuron populations still needs to be completed. Further exploration may lead to improved treatments for women who experience higher rates of depression compared to men (Ghosal et al., 2017). Developments and new insights in these fields will enable creative, innovative, and efficient treatment approaches, ultimately preventing stress-related disorders (Ghosal et al., 2017).

The inferior frontal lobe is a crucial part of the brain associated with the stress response, and more activation during intense mental stress may signal a more severe stress reaction (Moazzami et al., 2020). Data directly examining the contribution of change in the prefrontal structure and function to stress-induced extinction deficits currently needs to be provided (Wellman & Moench., 2019). Additionally, there needs to be more knowledge about the cognitive and neurological causes of stress-related disorders (Roberts & Mulvihill, 2024). Addressing these gaps will improve our understanding of the frontal lobe's function in stress-related disorders and lead to individualized and successful therapies, which will eventually benefit those who experience these conditions.

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